

Visualization of Places Based on Network Analysis through GIS

Win Win Shwe*

Abstract

Geographic Information System is a computer-based tool for mapping and analyzing feature events on earth. GIS technology integrates common database operations, such as query and statistical analysis, with maps. GIS can be used in many fields as a decision supporting tool for the best route, location selection, vehicle routing problem, optimization location information and attractive places selection. This research goal is to determine the best location for finding places. Then, in this research the three main interrelated subsystems express for any GIS application.

Key word: Geographic Information System, Subsystem, Vehicle Routing Problem

Introduction

Nowadays, time is considered as valuable as gold. Once time is used sensibly, access to a lot of information is possible. People who want to go in different places as tourists may need to have some information about those places. GIS can be used in many fields as a decision supporting tool for the best route, location selection, vehicle routing problem, optimization location information and attractive places selection.

GIS has a remarkable capacity to capture, manipulate, analysis spatial referenced data and it can display the result within a map or graphs. Moreover this technology can create links between various databases to assist a decision-making process.

This research will discuss the three main interrelated subsystems in any GIS application. And then, it will express the data acquisition, creation of spatial database, define layers, attribute data creation and spatial query. Finally, this research will emphasize to determine the best location for places.

Background Theory

GIS use for finding places Information

A Geographic Information System (GIS) is a computer-based tool for mapping and analyzing existent things and events that happen on earth. GIS technology integrates common spatial database operations such as query and statistical analysis with the unique visualization and geographic analysis benefits offered by maps.

It has a wide range of uses. For instance, GIS can also be used to determine the best location for finding places information. Most of spatial information is distributed through different places in different townships in city, which is more difficult to find interesting places because of the widespread interesting places information. Therefore, a better solution for this problem is the use of maps in order to present effectively the information.

Spatial Analysis

Spatial analysis is the process of manipulating spatial information to extract new information and meaning from the original data. Usually spatial analysis is carried out with a Geographic Information System (GIS). Spatial Analysis helps in identifying trends on the data, creating new relationships from the data, viewing complex relationships between data sets, and making better decisions.

The Importance of Geographic Information System

The ability of GIS to search databases and perform geographic queries has revolutionized many areas of science and business. It can be invaluable during a decision-

*Lecturer, Department of Computer Studies, Dagon University

making process. The information can be presented succinctly and clearly in the form of a map and accompanying report, allowing decision makers to focus on the real issues rather than trying to understand the data.

Because GIS products can be produced quickly, multiple scenarios can be evaluated efficiently and effectively. For this reason, in today's world, the ability to use GIS is increasingly important.

Using GIS as a Decision Making Tool

Using GIS as a decision-making tool, it is possible for decision maker to perform queries and analysis on complex and large volume of spatial and non-spatial data. These operations are usually more cost effective, accurate and faster than manual analysis, especially in situations where large volume of diverse data is involved.

The amount of data captured, stored and displayed determines the levels of awareness of the places information. The information can only be generated, well-packaged and presented by an information system which is known to be computerized system for creating, storing, manipulating and communicating information that are spatially referenced.

Subsystems in GIS Application

In any GIS application, there are three main interrelated subsystems, these are data acquisition, database management and information presentation subsystems. The data acquisition subsystem consists of appropriate hardware, software and procedure for collecting and/or processing spatial data using automated land surveying, analytical/digital photogrammetry, remote sensing, manual digitizing, and/or scanning methods. The database management subsystem deals with the storage, manipulation, analysis and retrieval of data acquired, using relevant hardware, software and procedure. The information presentation subsystem is concerned with the visualization and reporting of information in graphic and/or alphanumeric form using appropriate hardware and software components of the system.

Data Acquisition

A Yangon City map of the study area was used. Maps are fundamental tools used to portray spatial or geographic data. Data shown on maps vary with location. Map data are organized, classified, and depicted in a manner chosen by the map maker to optimize the map's effectiveness in communicating the nature of the data. Before geographic data can be used in a GIS, the data must be converted into a suitable digital format.

The process of converting data from paper maps or aerial photographs into computer files is called digitizing. Modern GIS technology can automate this process fully for large projects using scanning technology; smaller jobs may require some manual digitizing which requires the use of a digitizing table. When decision maker read a map, he or she is looking for patterns, linkages, or relationships in the map's data.

Creation of Spatial Database

Data is the core of the GIS and the most difficult part of it to assure. The most important action is to digitize the existing map by using ArcGIS software. In order to create the city map, it is necessary to consider first each thematic layer that contains each object. Then, the next step is the combination of these objects, such as roads, buildings, railways etc. The GIS database was structured to follow a relational database model format.

The summary of the procedure followed in the development of the spatial database included the following:

- Acquisition of the map of Yangon City.
- Field checking to determine the reliability of the map.
- Converting of the analogue map into digital format by scanning, georeferencing and digitizing.
- Editing to remove errors.
- Cartographic presentation.

Attribute Data Creation

Attribute data creation includes the following steps: compilation and addition of text information to features and vacations in tables, creation and editing of pictures and images to text labels, attaching images of respective feature location using the hotlink features. Table indicates how map maker elaborated the information about the layers and attributes for the different types of places.

Layers and Its Attributes

Name of Layer	Attributes
Road	FID, Shape, ObjectID, Shape, Linetype
Ward Area	FID, Shape, ObjectID, Shape, Name, Area
Tour	ID,FID, Shape, Type, Name, Location, Tour Photo
Hospital	ID,FID, Shape, Type, Name, Location

Define the Study Area

Yangon also known as Rangoon is a former capital of Burma (Myanmar) and the capital of Yangon Region. Although the military government has officially relocated the capital to Naypyidaw since March 2006, Yangon continues to be the country's largest city and the most important commercial centre. Yangon City Area is situated within Latitude (16.20'00" and 17.05'00") and Longitude (96.00'00" and 96.20'00"). This area is bounded by Hlaing River in the west, Yangon River in the south and Bago River in the East. The city is divided into four districts. The districts combined have a total of 33 townships. The total population of Yangon City is 4,348,000 (over four million). The total area is 231.18 sq mi (598.75 km²).

Yangon is a place full of places to visit and has main attractions in the city. The city has a variety of interesting sectors such as pagodas, beautiful parks, hotels, shopping centers, cinemas, markets, museum and so on. There are many different attractions to see and experience in Yangon. Visitors will be pleasantly surprised to find many places of interest which will keep them busy for many days.

Satellite map of Yangon City

Satellite map of Yangon City is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Satellite map of Yangon City

Road map of Yangon City

Road map of Yangon City is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Road map of Yangon City

GIS and Network Analysis

The heart of GIS is the analytical capabilities of the system. The selective display and retrieval of information from a database are among the fundamental requirements and an important facility of GIS. Geographical data used in Network Analysis have to be vector structure. Network Analysis is closely related to spatial interaction modeling. A set of geographic locations interconnected in a system by a number of routes. A network refers to a system of lines topologically structured. Arc-node topology is established for Network Analysis Query in GIS.

The simplest and the most apparent network application analyses are: street network analysis, traffic flow modeling, telephone cable networking, pipelines etc. Networks may be reduced to topological graphs, which are arrays of points connected or not connected to one another by lines. Common examples of networks include highways, railways, city streets, rivers, transportation routes (e.g., cars, buses, trains, and air), and utility distribution systems

(e.g., electricity, telephone, water supply, and sewage). Three principal types of network analysis are network tracing, network routing and network allocation.

Implementation of Places in Yangon City and Spatial Queries

The following map (Figure 3) illustrates the various layers of Yangon City.

Figure 3. Various layers of Yangon City

Data Analysis and Spatial Queries

The databases created tables were subjected to a number of spatial queries and analysis to assess the effectiveness of the GIS technology as a tool for finding places information. These queries and analysis would be useful for decision makers in performing their time and location management of the study area. Database query simply asks to see already stored information. Basically there are two types of query most general GIS allow query by attribute and query by geometry. GIS provides both simple point-and-click query capabilities and sophisticated analysis tools to provide timely information to decision makers and analysts alike. The ability of GIS to search databases and perform geographic queries has revolutionized many areas of science and business. It can be invaluable during a decision-making process.

Spatial Queries Results

These results can be achieved by queries in GIS Design and application for places:

- Determination of important and necessary places for decision maker.
- Determination of the best suitable places such as hotel, shopping centre etc.
- Determination of the optimum plan for places.
- Determination of the shortest distance between the selected places.

Figure 4. Spatial query and image of shopping centre in Yangon City

Figure 5. Spatial query and image of hotels in Yangon City

Conclusion

Geographic information systems (GIS) are a powerful set of tools for collecting, storing, and analyzing spatial data and giving valuable information to natural decision makers. The power of GIS lies not only in the ability to visualize spatial relationship, but also beyond the space to view of the locations with its many interconnected components and complex relationships. GIS however, have the capability to handle several types of information that can be related to a specific area.

GIS can visualize locational information at each stage during decision-making, including the output from location-selection models, using network analysis. A lot of information in various fields is necessary for decision making. In this research, GIS and network analysis were carried out by taking advantages of GIS possibilities for finding places. As a future work, how it integrates KBDSS with GIS could be used to support suitability analysis for spatial data and to find shortest route and quickest route. The approach involves GIS spatial data management, knowledge management technologies and KBDSS analysis model.

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Online Materials

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